

COMBINED BIOMETRIC AUTHENTICATION SOLUTIONS

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Annotation: Article illustrates biometric authentication solutions and focused on addressing problematic situations of biometric identification. An attempt was made to cover a number of problems with the help of the article and to show their simple solutions.

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Although, recently, systems such as "face + voice" are gaining popularity. This is due to the widespread use of communication tools that combine the modalities of audio and video, such as mobile phones with built-in cameras, laptops, video intercoms, and so on.

Combined biometric authentication systems are much more efficient than monomodal solutions. This is confirmed by many studies, including the experience of one bank, which installed a user authentication system first by face (error rate due to poor quality cameras 7%), then by voice (error rate 5% due to background noise), and after, by combining these two methods, they achieved almost 100% efficiency.

Biometric systems can be combined in various ways: in parallel, in series or according to a hierarchy. The main criterion when choosing a method for combining systems should be to minimize the ratio of the number of possible errors to the time of one authentication.

In addition to combined authentication systems, multi-factor systems can also be used. In systems with multi-factor authentication, the user's biometric data is used together with a password or electronic key.

Biometric Data Protection:

A biometric authentication system, like many other security systems, can be attacked by intruders at any time. The most common direction in the field of modern biometric authentication methods is the development of a protection strategy for biometric templates stored in databases. Among the most popular cybercrimes of today all over the world is "identity theft". Leaking templates from the database makes crimes more dangerous, since it is easier for an attacker to recover biometric data due to the reverse engineering of the template. Since biometric characteristics are inherent in their carrier, a stolen template cannot be replaced with an uncompromised new one, unlike a password. The danger of template theft also lies in the fact that in addition to

access to protected data, an attacker can get secret information about a person, or organize secret surveillance of him.

The protection of biometric templates is based on three main requirements:

- irreversibility - this requirement is focused on saving the template in such a way that it would be impossible for an attacker to reconstruct the biometric characteristics from the sample computationally, or to create physical fakes of biometric features;
- distinctness - the accuracy of the biometric authentication system should not be violated by the template protection scheme;
- revocation — the ability to generate several secure templates from one biometric data. This property provides the biometric system with the ability to revoke biometric templates and issue new ones when data is compromised, and also prevents comparison of information between databases, thereby maintaining the privacy of user data.

While optimizing robust template protection, the main challenge is to find an acceptable rapport between these requirements. The protection of biometric templates is based on two principles: biometric cryptosystems and transformation of biometric features. Recent changes in legislation prohibit the operator of a biometric system on their own, without the presence of a person, to change his personal data. Accordingly, systems that store biometric data in encrypted form become acceptable. You can encrypt this information in two ways: using a regular key and encryption using a biometric key - access to data is provided only in the presence of the owner of the biometric indicators. In conventional cryptography, the decryption key and the encrypted template are two completely different units. A template can be considered secure if the key is secure. The biometric key simultaneously encapsulates the cryptographic key template. In the process of encryption in this way, only partial information from the template is stored in the biometric system. It is called a secure sketch - secure sketch. Based on the secure thumbnail and another biometric sample similar to the one presented during registration, the original template is restored.

IT professionals researching biometric template security schemes have identified two main methods for creating a secure thumbnail:

- fuzzy commitment;
- fuzzy vault.

The first method is suitable for protecting biometric templates that look like binary strings of a certain length. And the second one can be useful for protecting patterns that are collections of points.

The introduction of cryptographic and biometric technologies has a positive effect on the development of innovative solutions to ensure information security. Particularly promising is multi-factor biometric cryptography, which combines the technologies of secret-sharing threshold cryptography, multi-factor biometrics, and methods for converting fuzzy biometric features into basic sequences.

It is impossible to form an unambiguous conclusion which of the modern biometric authentication methods, or combined methods, is the most effective for certain commercial ones in terms of price and reliability ratio. It is definitely seen that for many commercial tasks it is not logical to use complex combined systems. But, not to consider such systems at all is also not true. A combined authentication system can be activated taking into account the level of security required at the moment, with the possibility of activating additional methods in the future.

